

FORCED VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF INVERTED UMBRELLA ROOF SHELL USING ANSYS

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ABSTRACT:

A Inverted Umbrella Roof Shell, treated from the Analytical based software in ANSYS and Statistically aspects, is analyzed in this paper. In the Analytical sense, it is the solid shell of a great frequency and wide usability in a spatial structures, either as the complete form or in the parts. In the statistically regression analysis on graphs results sense, it is treated on the graphically results on which it is possible to determine the exact frequency on at each modes and field of the infinitesimal maximum deformations, and it is rigid by using Ferrocement.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The forced vibration analysis of a shell structures plays an important role in engineering applications as shells are widely used as structural components. Due to the limitations of the analytical methods for practical applications, numerical methods have become the most widely used as a tool for the designing of shell structures. One of the most popular numerical approaches for analyzing vibration characteristics of shells is the Finite Element Method (FEM). Shells of double curvature are found to be more advantageous than shells of single curvature. The very large spaces can be mastered only by doubly curved shells. A shell structure is a three-dimensional structure, thin in one direction and long in the other two directions. Such structures are abundantly found in nature, the shell of an egg is an impressive example. The development stemmed from the need to cover medium to large spans economically and from a fascination with a new material: reinforced concrete. Concrete shells include single curved shapes such as cylinders and cones and double curved geometries such as domes which are either synclastic (curves running in

the same direction) or anticlastic (curves running in opposite directions).

2. RELATED WORK

Li Hua and Ky. Lam (1996) [1] In this paper, the generalized differential quadrature (GDQ) method is used for the first time to study the effects of boundary conditions on the frequency characteristics of a thin rotating cylindrical shell. The present analysis is based on Love-type shell theory and the governing equations of motion include the effects of initial hoop tension and the centrifugal and Coriolis accelerations due to rotation. **Ljubica Velimirovic (2000) [2]** In this paper, a hyperbolic paraboloid, treated from the constructional and mathematical aspects, is analyzed. In the constructional sense, it is a thin shell of a great bearing capacity and wide usability in spatial structures, either as a complete form or in parts. **A.M. Nasir et al. (2001) [3]** In this paper, the free vibration and seismic response of hyperbolic shells, and examines the influence of thickness, height and curvature on this response. The response of the first lateral mode is also significantly affected by a change in the parameters. **Francesco Tornabene and Alessandro Ceruti (2012) [4]** In this paper, the static and dynamic analyses of laminated doubly-curved shells and panels of revolution resting on Winkler-Pasternak elastic foundations using the Generalized Differential Quadrature (GDQ) method.

3. METHODOLOGY

Inverted Umbrella shell Roof in quadrilateral ground plan are considered for the investigation. Numerical approach using the advanced finite element analysis based software called as ANSYS 15 is adopted. Based on the reported literature of similar nature FE model is developed and the study is conducted to investigate the behaviour of Inverted Umbrella shell Roof under the uniformly distributed Pressure load.

4. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Fig 1 Model of Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof applying pressure load on downward direction

Table 1 Material properties of Ferroccement

Properties	Ferroccement
Young's modulus	79056Mpa
Density	2000Kg/m ³
Tensile ultimate strength	250Mpa
Poisson's ratio	0.3

Table 2 Model Geometry For Inverted umbrella shell roof

Geometry parts		Ferroccement
Bounding Box	Length X	6000 mm
	Length Y	6000 mm
	Length Z	1110.7 mm
Statistics	Nodes	117728
	Elements	20808

DETAILS OF ELEMENT USED

In hyperbolic paraboloid inverted umbrella shell roof the quadrilateral fine element are used in ANSYS Solid186 element are used. This element is used for the three-dimensional modeling of solids. The element is found out by 117728 nodes in Inverted umbrella shell roof having six degrees of freedom at each node, translations in the nodal X, Y, and Z directions. This is also suitable for analyzing the thin to moderately-thick shell structures.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Finite Element Analysis of Inverted umbrella roof shell subjected to pressure load using Modal analysis for Ferroccement

Fig 2 Total def. of Mode 1 for Ferroccement
Fig 3 Total def. of Mode 2 for Ferroccement

Fig 4 Total def. of Mode 3 for Ferroccement

Fig 5 Total def. of Mode 4 for Ferroccement

Fig 6 Total def. of Mode 5 for Ferroccement

Fig 7 Total def. of Mode 6 for Ferroccement

Fig 8 Total def. of Mode 7 for Ferroccement

Fig 9 Total def. of Mode 8 for Ferroccement

Above Fig 2, Fig 3, Fig 4, Fig 5, Fig 6, Fig 7, Fig 8 and Fig 9 shows the frequency of Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof of eight modes of on the structure

Fig 10 Variation of Maximum deformation of Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof subjected to Forced vibration analysis using Ferroccement.

Fig 11 Variation of Frequency of Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof subjected to Forced vibration analysis using Ferrocement.

Above Fig 10 and Fig 11 shows the Variation of maximum deformation and frequency on inverted umbrella shell roof subjected to forced vibration analysis using ferrocement.

Table 3 Results of Maximum deformation and Frequency of Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof using Ferrocement compared with statistical regression analysis subjected to forced vibration analysis

Case		Ferrocement	R ²
Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof	Maximum def. (mm)	39.786 (3 rd mode)	0.0651
	Frequency (Hz)	90.129 (3 rd mode)	0.854

Above table shows the results of Maximum deformation on 3rd mode is 39.786mm and Frequency on 3rd mode is 90.129 and R² value of Maximum deformation is on statistical method means regression analysis on graphical representation is 0.0651 and Frequency is 0.854 respectively.

6. CONCLUSION:

In this study, The finite element analysis of static structural analysis and modal analysis were performed based software ANSYS (V15) for Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof (Hyperbolic paraboloid shell). Using Ferrocement material compared with regression statistical method on graphically representation.

1. The results obtained by the present analysis are accurate as seen in modal analysis also is compare with regression analysis.
2. The present analysis gives the realistic results of Maximum deformation for the Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof subjected to pressure load acting on top

face downward direction is in excellent agreement with that regression analysis.

3. From the graph we can conclude that Maximum deformation and frequency up to eight mode is excellent agreement with regression analysis using Ferrocement for Inverted Umbrella Shell Roof.

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